

A Paper on Digital Marketing With Reference To Consumer Perception

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Abstract

This Research Paper provides insight into current and future trends in marketing. The content is based on current literature and what is happening in the business world. It is emphasis on consumer response Towards Digital Marketing. Various articles, studies, reports, newspapers, magazines, various websites, and information on the internet are used for research. In India, which is pushing Digital Marketing on a massive scale, there is a fundamental shift towards digitalization. Consumers search the Internet more and more to find the best deals from sellers rather than traditional or traditional methods. In this study, acknowledged that businesses can really benefit from Digital Marketing such as search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, e-commerce marketing, campaign marketing, and social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, optical disks and games and are becoming more and more common in our New Technology Advancement. It is revealed that we are all connected through various online platforms like whatsapp and facebook and the increasing use of social media is creating new opportunities for digital marketers to attract and grab attention of the customers through digital platform. Awareness of consumer's motives is important because it provides a deeper understanding and knowledge about what influences users to create content about a brand or store. Digital Marketing is very cost effective and having a great commercial impact on the business and personal investments plans. Based on this study, it can further be argued that knowing which social media sites a company's target market utilizes is another key factor in guaranteeing that digital marketing will be successful and demand of future generation. You can analyze the effectiveness of digital marketing related to various companies. This study can be further extended to compare digital marketing techniques with specific techniques from different companies.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, strategy, Customer satisfaction, Channel for Digital Marketing

Introduction

The Digital Marketing is one of the major sources for advertising and content distribution via a variety of digital channels. Digital marketing includes various channels such as search engines, social media, email, applications, websites, and any modes that might arise with the possibility of advertisement. It is also includes offline channels that include Digital media as well as. The growth of digital media and digital platforms has made digital marketing the most attractive form of marketing mode. Even traditional channels are changing to fit more digital media into them, and that emphasizes its importance in a modern-day's marketing strategy. We will go more into what is digital marketing by exploring examples and the benefits it can provide you. Digital marketing is a non-conventional virtual platform basically on internet for promoting products, services, connecting customers, identifying and understanding needs of user using digital technologies and devices. It is one of most effective and prominent strategy to promote business at Large. Digital marketing plays important role for brand awareness and business development.

Digital marketing is one of the key strategies and processes for advertisers to connect and align with their audiences across digital channels. Ads themselves are creative elements shared across the digital inventory. This is the

space that publishers allocate for advertising on their platforms. Digital refers to many different channels; each uniquely used to connect and interact with audiences and achieve different goals in the conversion funnel.

Digital channels include display, search, mobile, social, video, and more. Interactive marketing is digital marketing that allows consumers to interact with advertisements and communicate with brands. The sheer amount of targeting technology and data collections in digital marketing means advertisers can reach both large audiences and more detailed segments without sacrificing scale. This includes the ability to target specific attributes such as demographics, behavior, and psychographics.

Marketers can not only target groups of people, but they can also target specific or specific devices, or even individual users regardless of what device they are using. At the same time, digital marketers are especially keen on measuring the success of their campaigns. A variety of user interactions can be tracked. B. Impressions, Clicks, Website Traffic, Leads, and Actual Purchases. As such, Digital media makes return on investment (ROI) easier to track than traditional media, helping marketers understand campaign effectiveness, optimize resources, and make better decisions moving forward

Statement of Problem

The growth in digital marketing in the past decade has been phenomenal and important. More and more people are tipping towards digital marketing because of its convenience and ease. Even with the massive spike in digital marketing and all its new avenues, the vast potential of conducting business digitalis largely untapped and covered. Moreover, there is still much room for digital marketing to grow. The review of literature reveals that most of the studies in this area are related to non-Indian context and hence there is an urgent need to analyze the risk perceptions in digital marketing. The present study is aimed to fulfill this requirement. This is a study of understanding whether risk matters or not in digital marketing and understanding risk perceptions in digital marketing. It is mainly help to understand about consumer response and perception regarding digital marketing.

Objective of the Study

1. To find out the satisfaction level of the customer in respect of Digital Marketing.
2. To understand about various online or digital platform for the market.
3. To find out the consumers satisfaction level and perception towards services provided through the Digital Marketing.

Sample Design and Size

In this research paper descriptive research design is used. Judgment and Convenience sampling method is used to get the accurate information about Digital Marketing. For conducting this research, a structured questionnaire is prepared. It indicates the numbers of people that is surveyed. Though large samples give more reliable results than small samples but due to constraint of time and money, the sample size was restricted to 50 respondents. The respondents belong to different age group.

Research Methodology

The Primary and secondary method used for data collection from website, Article, government sites, Journals etc. To complete the analysis of the collected data, descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations were implemented one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to determine whether various Digital Marketing factors influence the customer behavior.

Review of Literature

Rekha Dahiya (2017) The effect of Digital Marketing communication on product categories like books, music, fashion accessories, clothing, banking and digital gaming etc. has been well researched by the researchers; but automobile industry despite being one of the largest digital

spenders has faced dearth of academic studies especially in India. The present study aims to understand the effect of Digital Marketing communication on consumer buying decision process in Indian passenger car market. Mixed methodology was adopted for the study.

Madhubala (2018) This paper offers views on some current and future trends in Marketing, In this study, we acknowledged that businesses can really benefit from Digital Marketing such as search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, e-commerce marketing, campaign marketing, and social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, optical disks and games and are becoming more and more common in our advancing technology.

Need of Digitalization: Digitalization has played a crucial role in the fast advancement of global economy. In developed markets, Digital market is one of the most prominent and established platform. Organized Digitalization has a 75–80% share in total Marketing as compared with developing economies, where BTL Marketing activities has a dominant share. There is a local say “Be there where your customer Are” and Digitalization is enabling brand to remain where current customers stay i.e., in social media—Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram etc. Digitalization is maintaining its impressive growth in all type of markets, whether big or small. Big markets are countries that are always going to be e-commerce behemoths because of their size, and the smaller are promising markets where potential matters along with size. Recent verdict in high court of Kerala, consider Right to Internet as fundamental freedom and is a part of Right to education for mankind. In 2019, there are 1.92 billion Digital buyers in world, accounting for a quarter of world population with 4.39 billion users on Internet and 3.48 billion users active on social media with increase of 9% YOY. In 2014, Digital buyers were at 1.32 B expected to touch 2.14 billion by 2021, and over the next 5 years growth is expected to grow 21%. India, with world’s second highest population in India is a developing country where 627 million users are active on Internet with active buying at 273 million and with a growth rate of 20% increase for digital buyers. Digitalization has become very decisive platform for the product marketing and Brand Awareness.

Change in Consumer Behavior

Today’s consumer is tech savvy, socially empowered, information rich and lacking time. At the same time, technology is quickly evolving and embracing the needs resulted from new consumer motivations. Consumers’ ability to influence fellow consumers and companies alike is much bigger than

earlier generations. As a result, consumers expect the world at their fingertips, when they want it, how they want it and where they want it. Shopping is not a planned destination or event—they are shopping, 24/7 and they want an authentic shopping experience tailor-made specifically for them. 'Generation Z', want it all. They want to make an impact to the world and share all of their experiences on their journey. They strive to be authentic, socially sensible and in many cases value purpose over cost. They are driven by ambition and a strong moral conscience. They strive to independency, are more vocal and more informed than any generation before them. They are cognizant, engaged and choosy. They expect these standards are met by the businesses with which they deal with or take their business elsewhere. Furthermore, they will express their opinion, available for other fellow consumers to read.

Channels of Digital Marketing: Digital Marketing is incorporated and associated by different brands through various channels suiting their product and means of communicating to their buyers. It also depends on choosing best channels that give better ROI for brand. Most used channels of Digital Marketing are briefed below.

1. **Affiliate marketing:** It is perceived as a tool or device to produce demanded number of customers through independent marketer. It allows the brand to market its product through websites, create traffic and publish information. Individual work on behalf of brand using different tools of Digital and leveraging devices. This concept is also popularly known as website marketing where commission to marketer is received only on the sale of a product.
 2. **Display advertising:** It is one of most important concepts to use the display organic to attract traffic like used by Google AdWords. Through this small banner, gif images and videos are made to highlight the product or brands. It is one of effect method of DigitalMarketing where visual effect made to eye catch the traffic.
 3. **Email marketing:** This tool is very popular to communicate to the individual where the promoter is aware about the intender or buyer and communicate directly. This is one of the cheapest and Easy modes of Marketing and need to ensure effective content drafting. This email Marketing is sometime less preferred as the user gets irritated as spam email so the user interest is legal obligation to receive, unsubscribing leads to stop receiving such communications.
 4. **Search engine marketing:** It is a form of internet or online Marketing based on websites. It is one of paid type of DigitalMarketing
- concept through which traffic from search engine are brought to product or brand owing business websites. Search engine Marketing platforms are Google AdWords, Bing Ads, Yahoo search Ads.
5. **Search engine optimization:** Marketers use different factors and tactics to bring the website to achieve top ranks on organic search results through optimization of search engine. It is based on algorithm and content drafting through which the search are made to attract and Grab attention towards the traffic of business websites to the top of search engine.
 6. **Social media marketing:** It refers to the process of gaining or attracting traffic through social media sites. Paid Marketing also commonly known as social media Marketing includes promotion of content, websites or products through ads in several mobile apps, trusted and established channels like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Pinterest, Google+ etc. It is process of advertising on external social sites executed to draw attention of buyers. It is also based on remarketing activities like user, buyers visiting to buy products in Flipkart happens in a way like Flipkart ads follows him even when user is visiting Facebook, Yahoo, Rediff or so similar another social media platform.
 7. **Apps marketing:** Most trendy and popular mode of Digital Marketing .Promotion of brands in different apps is a new way of promoting products. There are different apps been built for various sections of human livelihood and finding spaces in between or on the app section is the better to reach specific and defined segment. Product related to specific app are also mapped and tie up done by Various brand so as persons using app are considered to have interest in app related products. To put this as an example, people using health app may be interested in buying health products and so any app promotion of protein products could be interested in segment of people using health apps
 8. **Web analytics:** It is the process of analyzing the behavior of traffic on websites and search engines through measures are decided which will promote and attract more traffic. It is the analyzing part of Digital traffic through which human behavior on platform are studied, used for researches so that more valued concept are brought suiting traffic. There are two common categories: onsite and offsite web analytics. Other frequent used DigitalMarketing channels are like Pay per click, Pop-up Ads, Match content ads, Floating Ads, Interstitial Ads,

Digital classified Ads, Frame Ads, Banners

Ads.

Data Analysis:-

Table.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents
n=50

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Category	Frequency/percentage
1	Gender	Male	30
		Female	20
2	Age	20-25 years	26
		25-30 years	24
3	Occupation	Student	28
		Job	22
4	Educational Qualification	Graduate	27
		Post Graduate	23
5	Family Monthly Income	Rs 20,000- Rs 30,000	10
		Rs 30,000- Rs 40,000	10
		Rs 40,000- Rs 50,000	17
		Rs 50,000- Rs 60,000	13

Table.2 Frequency distribution of the customers about factors affecting DigitalMarketing

Sr. No.	Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Transaction security and multiple payment options	22	13	3	2	0
2	Price is my primary concern for shopping online.	24	20	4	2	0
3	Personal privacy and security	17	20	10	2	1
4	Time saving is my main reason for shopping online.	13	22	11	4	0
5	The speed of access	19	21	9	1	0
6	After – sales service	12	23	6	6	3
7	Warranty or guarantee on the product	18	12	15	3	2
8	All time shopping accessibility	25	17	5	3	0
9	Shorter delivery period	9	11	22	2	6
10	Ease of product price and quality Comparison	16	24	7	3	0
11	Variety of globally available product	28	15	5	2	0
12	Customer’s review and product rating availability	15	25	3	6	1
13	Appearance of the DigitalMarketing website	14	21	8	5	2
14	Website provide sufficient product information and explanation	12	26	9	3	0
15	My colleagues influence me to go shopping online.	11	21	7	7	4

Result of Data Analysis

The **Table 3** provides some very useful descriptive statistics the mean, standard deviation for the dependent variables for all the groups and when all groups are combined (Total). The F ration value is 60.09731 and the P value is 0.00001 which is below

0.05 and therefore there is the significance difference in the consumer behavior of the students with regards to the various DigitalMarketing factors of customer behavior.

Table 3

Summary of data						
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
N	15	15	15	15	15	75
$\sum X$	248	291	122	50	19	730
Mean	16.5333	19.4	8.1333	3.3333	1.2667	9.7333
$\sum X^2$	4436	5961	1358	216	71	12042
Std. Dev.	4.897	4.7479	5.1111	1.8772	1.831	8.1677

Result Details				
Source	SS	Df	MS	
Between Treatment	3823.3333	4	955.8333	F=60.09731
Within Treatment	1113.3333	70	15.9048	
Total	4936.6667	74		

Findings:-

Significant differences existed among the customer behavior and the various Digital Marketing factors of the respondents.

Suggestions

1. Special offers can be given to make the customers to quantify and avail the effect of Digital Marketing. This will help international business to increase the overall business.
2. Update, monitor and analyze the status of the web site optimization on a periodical basis to assess the effectiveness of Digital Marketing.
3. Special training and R&D can be provided to understand the various new innovations that have happened in the website optimization field. This will motivate the customers to choose the Digital Marketing services.
4. Innovate and Create the SEO services to continue the good services in the website traffic building and also to get more customers.

Conclusion:-

In this study, an attempt was made to explore the factors influencing the online buying behavior of the customer. The main influencing factors for online shopping were identified as availability, low price, promotions, comparison, convenience, and customer service, perceived ease of use, time consciousness and variety seeking. Digital Marketing is an umbrella term for the Marketing of products or services using Digital technologies, mainly on the internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising and any other Digital medium Digital Marketing activities are Search Engine Optimization, Search Engine Marketing, content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing, and e-commerce marketing, social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, optical disks and games, and any other form of digital media. This study has also been undertaken to understand and explore about the overall effectiveness of the Digital Marketing

among random customers mainly youngsters. For this purpose, responses from the respondents of all age groups using Digital Marketing have been collected and analyzed. Based upon the findings out of the research, few valuable suggestions have been given to the markets mainly to improve the overall effectiveness of Digital Marketing in order to attract customers

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